

TEACHING STRATEGIES FOR CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES

Mirsalikova Nigina

Chirchik state Pedagogical University

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Abstract

This publication examines the approaches, strategies and technologies for teaching children with special educational needs in the context of inclusive education. A theoretical review of the studies of foreign authors and the latest works of domestic scientists was carried out. The author came to the conclusion that there is a continuity of research. The most preferred approaches were communicative, system-activity, constructivist and individual. There are also innovative alternative approaches.

Key words: children with special educational needs, inclusive education, theoretical review.

The relevance of research. Integration of "special" children into educational institutions are a natural stage of development special education systems. It's about rethinking society and the state of their attitude towards people with disabilities health opportunities, recognizing not only the equality of their rights, but also society's awareness of its obligation to provide such people with equal with all the opportunities in different areas of life, including education. Growing number of children with disabilities suggests the need to include such children in a full life society, which in turn makes it especially important to ensure their rights to complete education. Hence the growing popularity of the idea and practitioners of inclusive education. In international documents inclusive education is understood as a reform that supports and encourages diversity among students. Inclusive (French *inclusif* - including, from Latin *include* - I conclude, include) or included education is a term used four to describe the process of teaching children with special needs in educational institution. The basis of inclusive education an ideology is laid down that excludes any discrimination against children, which ensures equal treatment of all people, but creates special conditions for children with special educational needs. Inclusive education is a process of development of general education, which implies the availability of education for all, in terms of adaptation to the different needs of all, which ensures access to education for children with special needs. At the same time, the term "inclusive" means: "spread

over a wide a range of subjects ... an education that is equally accessible to all students”.

The law provides for the right every person to education, regardless of sex, race, nationality, language, origin, property, social and official position, place of residence, attitude to religion, beliefs, belonging to public associations, as well as other circumstances. Thus, inclusive education presupposes education not only for persons with disabilities, but also inclusion in educational environment of people of a different mentality, different upbringing and other different factors. Contemporary social and economic conditions require a unified open educational space, integration of educational systems based on educational dialogue based on multilingualism and polyculturalism, “the development and implementation of the ideal and status of a “European citizen”, brought up in the spirit of common European values, dialogue, openness to others and perception diversity of cultures...”. Inclusive education is such an organization of the learning process, in which all children, regardless of their physical, mental, intellectual, cultural, ethnic, linguistic and other characteristics, are included in the general education system and study at the place of residence together with their non-disabled peers in the same general education schools - in such general schools that take into account their special educational needs and give their students need special support Inclusive education of children with special needs together with their peers is the teaching of different children in the same class, and not in a specially dedicated group (class) at a general education school .

The basis for the formation of the concept of "inclusive education" was postulate that education is a fundamental human right and that it creates the basis for a more just society. Everyone has the right to education. Everyone, regardless of their individual qualities and problems with health. In modern education, the terms "integrated learning", "inclusive learning", "collaborative learning" widely and often are used as synonyms. However, they are not at all equivalent, each has its own meaning, and they are in relation to each other subordination. The most common term is "collaborative learning", including the other two. After all, the situation of co-education is achieved not only when students unite in a school (class), different in their psychophysical, speech, sensory, intellectual capabilities (and even in relation to an ordinary class one can hardly speak about the absolutely homogeneous composition of children), but also when, with fourteen certain socio-cultural conditions in one school (class) in the educational process unites children who differ in linguistic, national, racial, religious, gender, class, age or any other signs. Thus, the education of children with limited psychophysical

opportunities together with children with normative development – one of the many options for possible co-education. For ordinary learners, educational integration or inclusion means the freedom to choose between an inclusive and regular class with ensuring for them the quality and pace of learning provided for educational standard. One form of solving this problems and is the introduction and development of inclusive approaches.

To Unfortunately, it is obvious that not having received a decent education, as a rule, people with disabilities are forced to be closed in four walls of their house, forced to exist on a beggarly benefits. In fact, they are isolated from the possibilities full-fledged self-expression, the search for one's place in the world. The most important problem for a disabled person is the possibility of obtaining professions. At the same time, accordingly, the chance of finding a decent one increases. Work, which means to get the opportunity to integrate into society, to live more a fulfilling life.

Benefits of introducing inclusive education in our country:

- Education of goodwill and responsiveness in healthy children. Students learn to accept and appreciate people regardless of their differences and features;
- Adaptation and integration into society of children with disabilities health opportunities;
- Children with disabilities will receive a full-fledged school education and in the future will be able to choose their own worthy profession;
- Children with disabilities receive a real life experiences that prepare them for life in society; parents will not be so worried about the fact that the child studying in a remedial school.

To date, in the United States, special attention in the course of building education management system is given to the strategic planning. This aspect is also reflected in the system management of inclusive education. In the planning process inclusive education, it is necessary not only to determine its general concept, but also draw up an appropriate realistic plan actions. To date, within the framework of the foreign experience of the organization management systems for inclusive education formed four the main areas of work with people with disabilities health opportunities.

These areas include the following:

1. Widening participation. The idea behind this approach is based on implementation of the principle of expanding access to the educational environment. AT within the framework of practical experience in the management of inclusive education, such 17 model has become widespread in Europe, especially within the UK. This model is implemented by improving financial incentives for educational institutions, organizing strategic planning within them.
2. Mainstreaming. This model reflects the key the principle of inclusive education, designed to create in educational Institutions, an environment that allows people with disabilities not only to receive education in a public environment, but also to conduct leisure time with their physically healthy peers.
3. Integration. The Integration model, which is also widely used in schools in Europe, where conditions are created for the direct inclusion students with disabilities in the educational process.
4. Inclusion. This model is currently widely dissemination in the education system of the United States of America, where the idea of developing inclusive education has reached the most serious scale of its development.

The foundations of the Inclusion program of inclusive education were

Laid down in the United States back in 1973 as part of the “Rehabilitation Act” and law on the education of children with disabilities. Thanks to the introduction of this model in the educational system United States, the process of creating new educational institutions was started, and also the renewal of former schools and universities in accordance with the needs of students with disabilities. During this process, completely new technologies were used, which were aimed at creating optimal and comfortable conditions for implementation of educational programs, which also began be optimized in accordance with the new pedagogical task. At present, in most American schools and universities carry out large-scale work aimed at preparing not only the teaching staff, but also students and eighteen parents who do not have developmental disabilities. Educational environment and society should work within the framework of the implementation of a single common strategy – creating a single space in which children and adults are outside depending on the characteristics of their development could feel

full members of society who have equal access to all information technology capabilities that today provides US educational system.

Management of the system of inclusive education in the United States, in the first place turn, aimed at training qualified personnel, creating programs for the adaptation of children and adults with disabilities, formation and development of the material and technical base, which will be able to enable all students to have equal access to educational services. Speaking about foreign experience in building a management system inclusive education, it is impossible to ignore the impact on this the field of education, provided by the world public organizations.

Based on the above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Inclusive education should not supplant traditional forms effective assistance to children with disabilities, used in special educational institutions.

Thus, inclusive education should not to oppose, but to promote the interaction of two educational systems – general and special. Only in their interconnection and enrichment a child with disabilities will accumulate useful social experience, will find its place in society and will feel equal

member of society. It is necessary to deficiencies that have been highlighted to minimize and only then is it possible to reveal each child with the help of educational program, which is quite complex, but corresponds to his abilities and abilities.

Persons with special adaptive abilities (defects in hearing, vision, speech, intellectual insufficiency, etc.). In these cases, adaptation promotes application in the learning process and in everyday life

various special means of correction and compensation of disturbed or missing functions. Thus, the socio-pedagogical support of the family,

having a child with special adaptive abilities is carried out in accordance with several tasks: the normalization of the life of the child and the family,

the maximum possible development and support of functional 26

abilities of the child in accordance with his capabilities, counteraction

addiction development, education and family support in the process

rehabilitation. There is an urgent need for training, education and

development of children with special adaptive abilities in order to integrate them into public life. Inclusive education is the process of developing a common education, which implies the availability of education for all children, including children with special adaptive abilities.

By to a large extent, inclusive education is the result of the development of ideas humanism based on the exceptional value of human personality, its uniqueness, the right to a decent life, whatever its physical condition, the right to possess all the values of modern civilization. Among the main problems of inclusive education is the acute lack of qualified personnel, as well as insufficient training psychologists, educators, defectologists, tutors and social teachers. One of the most important factors in the successful adaptation of a child with disabilities in the conditions of education in educational institutions is a competent and responsible position teachers of the child, helping him to smoothly “join” the children’s team. After all, only knowing the mental and physical characteristics of the student can adequately cope with the task. Significant role in slowing down the development of inclusive education in Russia is played by the conservatism of society, namely, in to a greater extent, the opinions of parents of healthy children, who are not uncommon oppose their children studying with students, those with disabilities. However, this phenomenon directly depends on the territorial location of the educational institutions.

Another obstacle to the development of inclusive education Is the lack of technical equipment that is necessary child with disabilities to learn surrounding reality on a par with their peers. To a greater extent this is expressed in the physical inaccessibility of the external environment, namely

lack of ramps and elevators at home and at school, inaccessibility of transport between home and school, the absence of sound traffic lights at the crossing 29 road on the way to school, etc. These problems are most often are caused by insufficient financial support.

In general, carried out the study confirms the proposed hypothesis in full, in in particular: to conduct special events for the adaptation of students with disabilities in the educational activities; include students with disabilities health into active forms of educational and cognitive work during

Extracurricular time; use modern working methods (role class teacher as a tutor) with students and parents, which will allow implementing all the functions of

cooperation between the family and the school. Thus, it should be noted that the study of inclusive educational space within the school is sufficient topical issue requiring further research. Received our results require further reflection, many aspects require deeper study and interpretation, during which new areas of study will emerge.

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